

Exploring historical discontinuities in global energy scenarios: A model-based reappraisal of the Shared Socio-economic Pathways

Abstract

Global environmental scenarios, such as the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs), are central to decision-making under deep uncertainty but have been criticized for their lack of alternative economic futures. This study addresses these limitations by introducing selected SSPs into the Integrated Assessment Model *MORDRED*, which endogenizes economic, demographic, and biophysical variables through system-dynamic feedback relationships. By re-quantifying SSP2, SSP3, and SSP5 under two boundary conditions — without (SSP') and with (SSP'') biophysical feedbacks — it was examined how the incorporation of biophysical feedbacks into economic system analyses affects the plausibility and viability of the SSP storylines. While the SSP' implementations reproduce dynamics projected by previous SSP quantification exercises, introducing biophysical constraints in SSP'' variations generates nonlinear dynamics and historical discontinuities in socio-economic and environmental trajectories which are absent from, and incompatible with, the original SSPs. Projected developments include stagnation or collapse in final demand, demographic contractions, and major shifts in energy system evolution before the end of the 21st century. A positive feedback loop between environmental degradation, reduced productive capacity and declining energy efficiency emerges as a key driver of systemic instability. These findings challenge the implicit assumption of perpetual economic growth underpinning many global environmental scenarios and reveal that futures featuring economic stagnation and collapse are not only possible but plausible under less optimistic boundary conditions. Thus, current SSP-based assessments underestimate both the risks of climate–economy interactions and the scope of required institutional transformations to ensure societal resilience under biophysical constraints.

Keywords

Shared socio-economic pathways; climate scenarios; global environmental scenarios; integrated assessment modeling; limits to growth

1. Introduction

Global environmental scenarios, notably energy and climate scenarios, have come to occupy a key position in supporting decision making under deep uncertainty (DMDU), as facilitated by the IPCC (Lempert et al., 2024). Among these, a particular set of scenarios has gained prominence: the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) (O'Neill et al., 2017). The SSPs form part of a sophisticated scenario architecture (Kriegler et al., 2014) and have been used by the IPCC in its Sixth Assessment Report. The five storylines (SSP1–SSP5), which trace alternative socio-economic development pathways over the 21st century, have been widely applied in quantitative simulation studies (Lauer et al., 2024).

Within the SSP scenario architecture, socio-economic developments are treated separately from climate policies, climate impacts, and adaptation processes. This separation allows for isolated and counterfactual projections of economic (Dellink et al., 2017) and demographic (Kc & Lutz, 2014) developments. While this methodological choice simplifies modeling, it also neglects critical feedbacks between social, economic, and climatic systems. Consequently, the SSP storylines appear overly linear and fail to capture risks emerging from real-world interdependencies. As Szetey et al. (2023) highlight, modeling constraints narrow the SSP focus excessively, exemplified by the absence of intentional degrowth futures or other non-growth economic outcomes. Further criticisms include a lack of institutional realism and excessive optimism regarding the large-scale and timely implementation of decarbonization technologies (Lane & Montgomery, 2014).

According to Keys et al. (2024), the SSPs thus exhibit key features of *Anthropocene science*: limited “worlding capacity,” value-laden assumptions about what is possible, and a tendency to exclude alternative futures. In the context of DMDU, this last feature is especially problematic, as excessively linear futures obscure the need for policies that can respond to the complex and non-linear consequences of accelerating global environmental change.

However, despite calls for more diversity in global socio-economic climate and energy scenarios (El Skaf, 2025; Hickel et al., 2021; Otero et al., 2022; Rothman et al., 2023) and significant advances realized in the realm of modeling post-growth futures —whether through intentional societal transitions or unintentional economic contractions (Edwards et al., 2025; Lauer et al., 2025) —little is currently known about the implications of integrating biophysical feedback effects into economic system analyses, particularly regarding the plausibility and viability of the original SSP storylines.

This article addresses that gap by conducting a comparative scenario analysis using *MORDRED 1.0.2* (Model of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development), a system-dynamic, non-equilibrium Integrated Assessment Model in which key economic, demographic and biophysical variables evolve endogenously and are driven by complex feedback relationships. By simulating different variations of SSP2, SSP3 and SSP5, we test how scenario outcomes change once the assumption of continuous

economic growth is removed. Our approach can thus be described as an IAM-based quantitative study that anticipates potential future risks and aims to increase societal preparedness for discontinuous socio-economic changes during the 21st century (cf. Pereira et al., 2021). Additionally, we intend to explore how numerical projections of the SSPs vary when they are quantified with a model incorporating a fundamentally different structural logic.

Consequently, the remainder of the article is structured as follows: The remainder of the article is organized as follows: first, we provide an overview of the model and the adopted parameterization approach; next, we describe and compare the key simulation results from the SSP variations; and finally, we contextualize the simulation outcomes and discuss their policy relevance.

2. Methods

2.1. The MORDRED model

MORDRED (Model Of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development) is a global IAM designed to represent socio-economic inequality at global and regional levels and to incorporate key feedback relationships between its submodules. Built on a system dynamics framework, MORDRED endogenizes variables that are often treated as exogenous in other IAMs—such as economic growth, mortality and fertility rates, labor force evolution, and climate impacts. This structure provides the flexibility required to simulate a broad range of global environmental and economic scenarios. The model's principal components and feedback relationships are summarized in Fig. 1.

MORDRED is calibrated with data from the databases Exiobase3 (Stadler et al., 2018) and GCIP (Lahoti et al., 2016), as well as from climate, emissions and population data provided by the IPCC WGI (2021) and the UN (2019). It can be considered an ecological macroeconomic model (Hardt & O'Neill, 2017) due to the monetary input-output (IO) structure of its economic module and the linkages between the monetary economic structure and the biophysical components of the model, i.e., the energy, land, and climate system.

The economic module of MORDRED consists of a global input-output production matrix disaggregated into 25 sectors covering agriculture, biomass, industry, mining, services, transport, and various energy sectors. Sectors produce intermediate goods as well as consumption and investment goods demanded by the different final demand components (governments, households and Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF)). Production in each sector depends on intermediate goods and the primary production factors: capital, labor, land, and energy. The latter two are subdivided into specific types—such as agricultural and forest land, and fossil fuels, bioenergy, or electricity from various sources.

The demographic module represents 20 age groups (each spanning five years), three world regions—center (high-income countries), semiperiphery (upper-middle-income

countries), and periphery (lower-middle- and low-income countries)—and four social classes (subsistence, Top20, Middle50, and Bottom30). The subsistence class includes individuals living largely outside the global capitalist economy; its size is set to zero in the center at the model's initial time step. Within each region, the population participating in the formal economy is divided into deciles, with the richest two deciles forming the Top20 class, the poorest three the Bottom30 class, and the remaining five the Middle50 class. In the SSP simulations, parameters governing the integration of the subsistence class into the formal economy lead to rapid assimilation; consequently, this class is omitted from the analysis, as global population quickly converges to that of the formal economy. Population segments generate consumption demand that drives economic development, while mortality and fertility rates for each age cohort evolve with per-capita consumption. The population aged 15–64 constitutes the potential labor force of the global economy.

The land, energy and climate modules form the bridge between economic production and environmental impacts. They enable the calculation of emissions from land-use change and fossil fuel combustion. The climate module uses information from the land and energy module as well as various sectoral emission intensities belonging to the economic module to convert different greenhouse gas emissions (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, HFC, PFC, SF₆) into changes in global average temperatures with respect to the 1850 reference level.

The key feedback mechanisms embedded in MORDRED include:

- restrictions on economic production due to limited labor supply (demography → economy);
- constraints on population growth due to limited economic output (economy → demography);
- depletion of fossil resources driven by economic activity (economy → energy);
- reduced economic production from rising energy extraction requirements (energy → economy);
- expansion of land use from economic growth (economy → land);
- limits on production from land scarcity and conversion constraints (land → economy);
- increased emissions from economic output (economy → climate); and
- economic impacts resulting from temperature change (climate → economy; climate → labor → economy; climate → land → economy).

A detailed description of the model's development, full structure, and governing equations is provided in Lauer & Llases (2025).

For our simulations, we developed a new version of the model (MORDRED 1.0.2), characterized by the endogenization of sectoral energy intensity developments, i.e.

sectoral energy intensity evolves as a function of sectoral output per capita, which depends on demographic, economic and biophysical changes during the scenario simulation (see Supplementary Material (SM) 1 and Table 1).

Fig. 1: Structural overview of MORDRED 1.0.2.

2.2. Scenario assumptions and parametrization

We conducted a comparative scenario analysis of three SSPs: SSP2, SSP3 and SSP5. SSP2 features a continuation of historical trends, SSP3 an increase in regional competition and security concerns, and SSP5 a strong growth in fossil-based industrialization and consumption around the world (O'Neill et al., 2017). Apart from SSP1, the selected SSPs are used most frequently in the literature (Lauer et al., 2024) and are sufficiently distinct for a comparative analysis.

For every selected SSP scenario, we ran two simulations: In the first simulation (SSP'), the feedback loops from the environment on the economy were deactivated and very optimistic assumptions were made regarding the future evolution of input factors into economic production processes. In the second simulation (SSP''), biophysical restraints were activated and less optimistic assumptions regarding the availability of input factors were adopted to explore the effects of biophysical feedback loops on the viability of the original SSP storylines.

In parameterizing SSP2, SSP3, and SSP5, we sought to balance comparability with previous SSP quantifications and the preservation of MORDRED's structural and dynamic features. To this end, we drew upon the extended SSP storylines from O'Neill et al. (2017) and the corresponding quantitative and qualitative information provided in the main scenario quantifications (Calvin et al., 2017; Fricko et al., 2017; Fujimori et al., 2017; Kriegler et al., 2017; Riahi et al., 2017).

Unlike IMAGE, MESSAGE-GLOBIOM, AIM/CGE, GCAM, and REMIND-MagPIE, which underlie the main SSP quantifications (Riahi et al., 2017), MORDRED excludes carbon capture and storage (CCS) and bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) technologies, given concerns about their scalability and socio-ecological implications (Braun et al., 2025; Creutzig et al., 2021; Heck et al., 2018; Sekera & Lichtenberger, 2020). Biomass-based energy technologies are represented as a single aggregated sector. Similarly, agricultural production from various crops and livestock types is consolidated into one sector; therefore, MORDRED does not explicitly model crop yields or diet-related caloric intake. The relationship between diets, caloric intake, and life expectancy is captured indirectly through the consumption-based endogenization of mortality and fertility rates, since higher consumption implies dietary and nutritional changes (Ezzati et al., 2005; Gerbens-Leenes et al., 2010; Knez et al., 2017). MORDRED also departs from conventional IAMs by not relying on carbon or energy prices to shift the energy mix during simulations. Instead, technological progress and extraction constraints are reflected through changes in the input coefficients of the model's A matrix (cf. section 1 SM1).

We test the feasibility of the SSP storylines under two conditions: (1) without biophysical constraints and feedback mechanisms (SSP2', SSP3', SSP5'), and (2) with activated biophysical constraints and feedback mechanisms (SSP2'', SSP3'', SSP5'').

Table 1 summarizes the implementation of all SSP variations simulated in MORDRED. SM1 provides further details on the parametrization process, while SM 2 lists the numerical values used in all SSP configurations. Additionally, SSP variations with only a partial activation of biophysical feedback were conducted which are described and depicted in section 3 of SM1.

Variable	Basis for parametrization	Implementation	SSP2'	SSP2''	SSP3'	SSP3''	SSP5'	SSP5''	
Population	-		endogenous in MORDRED						
GDP per capita	O'Neill et al. (2017)	desired per capita household consumption in 2100 (<i>DC</i>) and desired growth rate (<i>dg</i>) per year	MEDIUM		LOW		HIGH		
	Calvin et al. (2017)		<i>DC</i> : 21,344 € (<i>dg</i> : varies between different world regions and consumption classes [1.75%- 2.13%])		<i>DC</i> : 7,749 € (<i>dg</i> : same for all regions and classes: 0.74%)		<i>DC</i> : 53,508 € (<i>dg</i> : varies between different world regions and classes [2.75 % - 3.41%])		
<i>Energy demand</i>									
Traditional fuel use	Riahi et al. (2017)	no traditional fuel use	-						
Lifestyles / material intensity	Riahi et al. (2017)	Input coefficients column in A matrix for the service sector are multiplied with a material intensity change factor $\alpha_{material}$.	materially intensive				very materially intensive		
	own choice		$\alpha_{material} = 0.95$				$\alpha_{material} = 1.1$		
Environmental awareness	Riahi et al. (2017)	changes in households', governments' and investments' sectoral consumption shares	MEDIUM		LOW				
	own choice		shift 90% of fossil electricity demand and 40% of nuclear electricity demand to renewable electricity; substitute 10% of non-electricity demand with renewable electricity		no changes compared to initial moment of the simulation				

			demand for households, governments and investment		
Energy intensity of industry	Riahi et al. (2017)	Input coefficients from energy sectors for the column of the industry sector (s=5) are multiplied by a factor α_{ei} that changes with sector output per capita.	MEDIUM	HIGH	MEDIUM
	own choice		$\alpha_{ei_{5SSP}} = \beta_5 * x_{5pc(t)}^\gamma + \varepsilon_5$ $x_{5pc(t)} \text{ grows faster in SSP5 than in SSP2, and slowest in SSP3. Thus, } \alpha_{ei_{5SSP5}} < \alpha_{ei_{5SSP2}} < \alpha_{ei_{5SSP3}}.$		
Energy intensity of buildings	Riahi et al. (2017)	Input coefficients from energy sectors for the column of the sector containing real estate (s=7) are multiplied by a factor α_{ei} that changes with sector output per capita.	MEDIUM	HIGH	MEDIUM
	own choice		$\alpha_{ei_{7SSP}} = \beta_7 * x_{7pc(t)}^\gamma + \varepsilon_7$ $x_{7pc(t)} \text{ grows faster in SSP5 than in SSP2, and slowest in SSP3. Thus, } \alpha_{ei_{7SSP5}} < \alpha_{ei_{7SSP2}} < \alpha_{ei_{7SSP3}}.$		
Energy intensity of transportation	Riahi et al. (2017)	Input coefficients from energy sectors for the column of the transport sector (s=21) are multiplied by a factor α_{ei} that changes with sector output per capita.	MEDIUM	HIGH	MEDIUM
	own choice		$\alpha_{ei_{21SSP}} = \beta_{21} * x_{21pc(t)}^\gamma + \varepsilon_{21}$ $x_{21pc(t)} \text{ grows faster in SSP5 than in SSP2, and slowest in SSP3. Thus, } \alpha_{ei_{21SSP5}} < \alpha_{ei_{21SSP2}} < \alpha_{ei_{21SSP3}}.$		
<i>Energy types</i>					
Importance of fossil fuels compared to	Kriegler et al. (2017), Fricko et al. (2017)	shifts in the input coefficients in A matrix between the fossil	MEDIUM	HIGH	HIGH

renewable energies and nuclear energy	own choice	electricity, nuclear electricity, hydro, solar PV and wind electricity sectors; electrification of key sectors	shift 70% of fossil electricity demand and 10% of nuclear electricity demand to renewable electricity; key economic sectors: electrification of 20% of non-electric input through renewable electricity	shift 40% of fossil electricity demand for production to renewable electricity; shift 50% of nuclear electricity demand to fossil electricity; key economic sectors: electrification of 10% of non-electric input through renewable electricity				
Technological progress in energy technologies	Kriegler et al. (2017), O'Neill et al. (2017)	Input coefficients from main energy sectors (es=3,10,12,13,14,15,17)	MEDIUM	LOW	HIGH			
	own choice	for the columns of energy sectors are multiplied by a factor α_{ei} that changes with sector output per capita.	$\alpha_{ei_{esSSP}} = \beta_{es} * x_{espc(t)}^\gamma + \varepsilon_{es}$ <p>The greater the output growth of an energy technology, the greater the intensity gains, i.e. technological progress.</p>					
<i>Fossil energy supply</i>								
Fossil fuel availability	Riahi et al. (2017)	quantity of fossil fuel resources	MEDIUM		MEDIUM		HIGH	
	Fricko et al. (2017)		169000 EJ	83900 EJ (lower value for oil and gas resources and upper value for	284000 EJ	83900 EJ	589700 EJ (highest estimates of all fossil fuel types in the literature)	353900 EJ (lower value for oil, gas and coal resources)

				coal reserves)				
<i>Agriculture & land use change</i>								
Land use change regulation	Riahi et al. (2017)	limit on primary forest conversion	MEDIUM		LOW		MEDIUM	
	own choice		protect 50% of primary forest area in 2019	no protection		protect 50% of primary forest area in 2019		
Land productivity growth	Riahi et al. (2017)	annual growth in land productivity	MEDIUM		LOW		HIGH	
	Fricko et al. (2017); own choice for SSP5' based on Fricko et al. (2017)		annual average increase of 3% for all land types	annual average increase of 0.53% for all land types	annual average increase of 2% for all land types	annual average increase of 0.35% for all land types	annual average increase of 4% for all land types	annual average increase of 0.795% for all land types
Environmental impact of food consumption	Riahi et al. (2017)	cropland and pasture demand of the food and agricultural sector	MEDIUM		HIGH			
	own choice		75% of original land intensity	90% of original land intensity				
Inequality between societies	O'Neill et al. (2017)	inequality in per capita consumption between classes	HIGH				MEDIUM	
	own choice		maintenance of the consumption p.c. ratios between classes				Reduction of consumption ratios between classes: the growth rate of the M50 class is kept constant, the consumption of the B30 class is multiplied by 1,05 and of the T20 class by 0.925.	

Inequality within societies	O'Neill et al. (2017)	inequality in per capita consumption between regions	MEDIUM	HIGH	MEDIUM
	own choice		20% reduction in the average consumption ratios between the center and the semiperiphery ($c_c:c_{s,2100} = 0.8 * c_c:c_{s,2019}$) and 25% reduction between the center and the periphery	maintenance of the consumption p.c. ratios between regions	20% reduction in the consumption ratios between the regions ($c_{center}:c_{i,2100} = 0.8 * c_{center}:c_{i,2019}$ with $i \in \text{semiperiphery, periphery}$)
Labor productivity growth	O'Neill et al. (2017)	annual growth of labor productivity	MEDIUM	LOW	HIGH
	own choice		increase of 3% p.a.	increase of 1.5% p.a	increase of 4% p.a.
Capital intensity growth	O'Neill et al. (2017)	annual growth of capital intensity	MEDIUM	LOW	HIGH
	Kriegler et al. (2017); own choice for SSP3 based		increase of 16.1% until 2100 with respect to initial value	increase of 10.0% until 2100 with respect to initial value	increase of 22.6% until 2100 with respect to initial value
Non-combustion related GHG intensity reduction	Riahi et al. (2017)	non-combustion related (e.g. CH4, N2O, SF6) target GHG intensity	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW
	own choice		reduction of 20% until 2100 with respect to initial intensities	reduction of 10% until 2100 with respect to initial intensities	reduction of 5% until 2100 with respect to initial intensities
Other MORDRED	MORDRED	-	MORDRED baseline value		

scenario variables								
Climate impacts	MORDRED	damage factors	deactivated	activated	deactivated	activated	deactivated	activated
Land, energy and labor scarcity factors	MORDRED	scarcity factors	deactivated	activated	deactivated	activated	deactivated	activated

Table 1: Overview of SSP parametrization in MORDRED.

3. Results

3.1. SSP implementation without biophysical feedbacks

Scenario simulations of the SSP storylines without biophysical feedbacks generally confirm previous SSP quantifications produced with different IAMs (Fricko et al., 2017; Fujimori et al., 2017; Kriegler et al., 2017; Riahi et al., 2017). Historical discontinuities are absent, and the quantitative patterns align with the qualitative descriptions of the respective scenarios. This applies to demographic, macroeconomic, energy, and food system developments. As a result, climate conditions change rapidly over the simulation period (2019–2102).

3.1.1. Demographic and macroeconomic developments

In SSP2', world population grows moderately until 2057, reaching 8.8 billion, then stabilizes before declining to 8 billion by 2100. The population of the *center* (high-income countries) shrinks continuously to 790 million, while the *semiperiphery* (upper-middle-income countries) grows to 3 billion in 2034 before gradually declining to 2.5 billion. The *periphery* (lower-middle- and low-income countries) peaks later, at 4.96 billion in 2074, and slightly declines to 4.8 billion by 2100. Thus, while global population in 2100 is comparable to current levels, the relative demographic weight of the Global South increases considerably.

The population decline results mainly from falling fertility rates that outpace mortality reductions, driven largely by rising per-capita consumption and, to a lesser extent, higher government spending on education. Global average consumption per capita more than triples, reaching €21,669 per year by 2100, supported by steady growth in final demand, which nearly quadruples to 308.5 trillion (2019-€).

In SSP3', slower economic growth delays the population peak to 2064 at 8.9 billion, followed by a gradual decline to 8.6 billion by 2100. The center and semiperiphery show patterns similar to SSP2', while the periphery, in line with the SSP3 storyline, continues to grow until 2093, peaking at 5.2 billion. Global final demand reaches €115.7 trillion—only 37.5% of the SSP2' level. The lower productive development coupled with the higher population leads to a lower average consumption per capita level of 7,882€ per year in 2100 which is still considerably higher than the initial average consumption level. However, given the high level of inequality in this scenario, the average consumption in the periphery is only 3,705 € per year in 2100.

In the SSP5' simulation, world population peaks earlier, in 2056, at 8.7 billion and declines faster than in SSP2', reaching 7.8 billion by 2100. This is accompanied by very high growth in global final demand (819 trillion €/year in 2100, more than ten times the initial level) and average per-capita consumption (55,196 €/year, almost nine times the initial level).

Fig. 2 resumes the main demographic and macroeconomic developments for the three scenario implementations in MORDRED at the global level.

Fig. 2: a) World population, b) Global final demand, c) Consumption per capita on the global level for the scenarios SSP2' (blue), SSP3' (grey) and SSP5' (red).

3.1.2. Sectoral evolution of the economy

In SSP2', final energy use grows across all types throughout the simulation. Fossil fuel energy increases from 291 EJ in 2019 to 539 EJ in 2100. Electricity use rises sharply, accelerating toward the end of the period to 330 EJ. Electricity production quadruples, biomass energy more than doubles to 108 EJ, and renewable electricity—hydro, wind, and solar PV—reaches 82, 94, and 93 EJ, respectively, meaning each technology alone could meet current global electricity demand.

In line with the macroeconomic and demographic developments, final energy demand grows more slowly in SSP3', and although wind and solar PV expand exponentially, they reach only 21 EJ and 20 EJ by 2100. Conversely, in the SSP5' simulation, final energy demand surges: non-electric fossil energy reaches 1,424 EJ, biomass 281 EJ, and electricity 713 EJ—almost nine times the 2019 level—while the renewable share of electricity remains lower than in SSP2'.

Rising affluence in all scenarios reduces the food sector's share of total output, as higher incomes shift consumption toward other goods and services. The decline is steepest in SSP5'. In SSP3', however, the food sector share initially rises to 6.7% by 2027 due to the larger proportion of poorer populations, before declining later. Despite its reduced share, total food sector output grows exponentially in SSP5', reaching €69 trillion by 2100, compared to €13 trillion in SSP3'.

Fig. 3 summarizes energy and sectoral developments across SSP2', SSP3', and SSP5'.

Fig. 3: Annual quantity of a) fossil fuels; b) electricity; c) biomass used by the global economy for SSP2' (blue), SSP3' (grey) and SSP5' (red). d) Evolution of renewable electricity systems (hydro, wind and solar PV based electricity) in the three scenarios; e) share of the food sector in total output on a global scale; f) annual total output of the food sector.

3.1.3. Emissions and global climate change

In line with the macroeconomic developments and the evolution of the global energy system, SSP5 emits the highest quantity of greenhouse gases and reaches the highest global temperatures, while SSP3 displays the lowest emissions and temperature increases, with SSP2 being situated in the middle.

In SSP5, GHG emissions resulting from strong economic growth and reliance on fossil fuels continue unabated and reach 325 Gt in 2100, corresponding to a temperature change of 5.98 °C compared to 1850. In SSP2, annual emissions increase to 100 Gt by 2100, resulting in a 3.71 °C warmer world. SSP3 shows a slower rise, from 50 Gt to 59 Gt, leading to 3.02 °C of warming (Fig. 4).

Other SSP quantifications project comparable temperature outcomes for SSP2 (3.76 °C by 2100), significantly higher global warming under the SSP3 baseline (4 °C in 2100) and significantly lower levels of climate change under SSP5 baseline (5 °C in 2100)

(Riahi et al., 2017). These differences stem mainly from the parametrization of the energy system and the assumptions made for the endogenization of energy intensities.

Fig. 4: a) Total greenhouse gas emissions and b) global average temperature change for the three SSP' simulations (blue: SSP2', grey: SSP3', red: SSP5').

3.2. SSP implementation with biophysical feedbacks

Including biophysical feedbacks leads to major deviations from previous SSP quantifications, revealing radically altered global trajectories characterized by strong historical discontinuities absent from the original storylines.

3.2.1. Demographic and macroeconomic developments

Introducing biophysical constraints produces significant demographic changes in the final quarter of the century. In SSP2'', population follows SSP2' until 2065, then declines more slowly before dropping sharply from 2092, falling from 8.4 to 6.6 billion by 2100. This illustrates that moderate climate impacts – through their adverse effects on the per capita consumption of different socio-economic groups and world regions – could lead to a relative increase in the population due to a relative increase in overall birth rates while severe climate impacts are linked to a population decline due to escalating mortality rates. Regionally, the decline is concentrated in the *periphery* (from 5 to 3.3 billion), while the center and semiperiphery maintain slightly higher populations than in SSP2', due to higher birth rates.

Tighter biophysical limits in SSP2'' constrain final demand throughout the simulation, causing a lower growth in economic production. Global final demand peaks in 2077 at €129 trillion—ten years after divergence from SSP2' and 15 years before the population

collapse. By 2090, it is 46% below its peak, and by 2100, 38% below the initial 2019 level (Fig. 5b). Average global consumption per capita rises with final demand, reaching a peak at about 7,750 €, and subsequently declines strongly to a minimum of less than 3,200 € in 2096. Since the rate of decline in the world population eventually exceeds the rate of decline in final demand average per capita consumption increases slightly during the last 5 years of the simulation (Fig. 5c).

SSP3'' exhibits similar dynamics but with earlier discontinuities. Population matches SSP3' until 2086, then falls by 35% within 15 years. As in SSP2'', the deep-rooted consumption inequality of the world economic system has the effect that different world regions are affected unequally by biophysical constraints to growth. As a result, in the simulation the periphery loses 65% of its population size while changes in birth and death rates in the center and the semiperiphery are not drastic enough to cause a demographic collapse. In the periphery, mortality rates spike due to the massive spread of extreme poverty among the poorer classes that see their consumption levels decline as the global economy starts to contract due to mounting climate change impacts and rising fossil resource extraction costs.

The SSP3 storyline assumes a less favorable global economic panorama, which is reflected in low growth rates in both SSP3 simulations. Thus, once biophysical limits to growth are introduced, global final demand peaks at 111 trillion € in 2076 in SSP3'', i.e. slightly earlier and at a lower level than in SSP2''. Interestingly, until its peak, final demand in SSP3'' grows faster than in SSP3'. However, disaggregating final demand into its components, we find that this difference is driven by a strong increase in investment which becomes necessary to prevent climate impacts from halting economic growth, and to ensure the accessibility of fossil resources. Conversely, consumption in the different world regions and classes already peaks more than a decade before the observed peak in world demand. This points to the possibility of global futures that feature a stagnation in living standards or even rising poverty levels despite growing final demand and production.

Although global final demand in SSP3'' peaks at a lower level than in SSP2'', by the end of the century the difference has reduced significantly (Fig. 5b), and – due to the earlier and higher population decline – average consumption reaches its minimum at an earlier and a higher level than in SSP2'' (Fig. 5c). Thus, paradoxically, average consumption by the end of the scenario is higher in SSP3'' than in SSP2'' despite the global panorama is undoubtedly less favorable. Although representing GDP (or consumption) per capita is common in modeling exercises concerned with future socio-economic developments—and implicitly serves as a proxy for well-being—substantial criticism has been raised regarding the use of GDP per capita as an indicator of population well-being at the national level (Aitken, 2019; T. Dong et al., 2024; Harvie et al., 2009; Kubiszewski et al., 2013). This critique applies even more strongly at the global level, where an even higher degree of aggregation obscures territorial, class, and gender inequalities. We therefore conclude that world average consumption (and even more so world GDP) per capita

does not constitute an adequate indicator of well-being or living standards, particularly during periods of economic crisis and unintentional economic degrowth.

The demographic trajectory of SSP5'' differs markedly: population follows SSP2'' but remains stable at the century's end, at 0.4 billion higher than in SSP5'. Global final demand continues to grow but at lower rates, reaching 152 € trillion—only 19% of SSP5' level. Growth in average consumption per capita levels slows down during the last decade of the simulation, peaks at 8,665 € per year in 2099 and then starts to decline. Again, this points to the possibility of a relative growth in investment goods and a relative decline in consumption goods in futures with significant climate change impacts, affirming that treating GDP as a central variable in research around future world economic and environmental developments is problematic due to its lack of differentiation between the benefits and cost of economic growth, the latter including necessary productive activity to alleviate the impacts of ecological degradation (Van den Bergh, 2009). Importantly, the lack of population and final demand decline in this scenario during the 21st century does not mean that this scenario is more feasible or stable than the other simulations in the mid- to long-term. Rather, the peak in average consumption per capita at the end of the century suggests that SSP5'' may be approaching a turning point beyond the temporal scope of this analysis.

Fig. 5: a) World population, b) Global final demand, c) Consumption per capita on the global level for the scenarios SSP2'' (blue), SSP3'' (beige) and SSP5' (pink).

3.2.2. Sectoral evolution of the economy

Reflecting the demographic and macroeconomic discontinuities, sectoral dynamics diverge sharply from the SSP' simulations. In SSP2'' and SSP3'', final energy production from fossil fuels and electricity peaks at the end of the 2070s. The higher carbon intensity of the economy in SSP3'' results in fossil fuel pathways comparable to SSP2'', while electricity growth is significantly higher in SSP2'' and remains comparable to SSP5'' until the global economic downturn begins in SSP2''. Biomass production for bioenergy also peaks at the end of the 2070s, reaching 60 EJ in both scenarios (Fig. 6a-c). Conversely, in SSP5'', final energy use continues to grow throughout the century across

all energy types, albeit at a much slower rate than in SSP5'. By 2100, global production reaches 420 EJ of fossil fuels, 177 EJ of electricity, and 75 EJ of biomass—equivalent to 29%, 25%, and 27% of the respective SSP5' values. Thus, in relative terms, SSP5'' relies even more heavily on fossil fuels than SSP5'.

The renewable electricity sectors also exhibit discontinuous changes. In SSP2'', hydroelectricity declines to less than 25 EJ annually after peaking at 37 EJ in the late 2070s. The decline in global final demand, however, only temporarily slows the exponential growth of wind and solar PV (Fig. 6d). SSP3'' reproduces the same pattern but at generally lower levels of renewable electricity, particularly for wind and solar energy. Finally, the expansion of renewables in SSP5'' is slower than in SSP2'' throughout the simulation for both solar PV and wind-based electricity, while hydroelectricity in SSP5'' surpasses that in SSP2'' only when final demand starts to decline in the latter scenario.

The evolution of the global food sector's output mirrors the trajectory of final demand in all simulations (Fig. 6f). Following a moderate but steady decline in its share of total output, this share increases again during the last three decades of the simulation in SSP2'' and SSP3'' due to shifting household consumption patterns: as overall budgets fall sharply, households allocate a larger proportion of spending to food. However, ultimately, the dramatic surge in mortality rates of the poorest households at the global level lead to a strong reduction in the weight of the consumption of the poorest classes, and, consequently, the share of the food sector in total output decreases again (Fig. 6e). In contrast, in SSP5'', the food sector's output share declines moderately, stabilizes at 6% from 2080 onward, and begins to rise slightly after 2088—signaling a turning point in the global economy and foreshadowing major structural transformations in the 22nd century.

Fig. 6: Annual quantity of a) fossil fuels, b) electricity, c) biomass used by the global economy for SSP2'' (blue), SSP3'' (beige) and SSP5'' (pink). d) evolution of renewable electricity systems (hydro, wind and solar PV based electricity) in the three scenarios, e) share of the food sector in total output on a global scale, f) annual total output of the food sector in the three SSP'' scenarios.

3.2.3. Emissions and global climate change

Compared to the SSP' simulations, the SSP'' variations result in significantly lower global GHG emissions throughout the simulation period. In SSP2'' and SSP3'', global GHG emissions peak in 2077 and 2076 at 88 and 94 Gt/year, respectively, whereas in SSP5'', emissions continue to rise until the end of the century, reaching 95 Gt. The local emission peaks observed in SSP2'', SSP3'', and SSP5'' (Fig. 7b) stem from rapid land-use conversions from forests to agricultural land, driven by the lower land productivity assumptions in the SSP'' implementations. Consequently, global primary forests are completely deforested in SSP3'' by 2076, causing a temporary emission spike, while in SSP2'' and SSP5'', a primary forest protection policy preserves 50% of the initial primary forest until the end of the simulation.

Due to the highly non-linear emission dynamics in the SSP'' simulations, the increase in global average temperature is less monotonic than in the SSP' scenarios. In SSP2'' and SSP3'', the rise in global temperatures slows toward the end of the simulation, reaching 3.37 °C and 3.41 °C in 2100, respectively, whereas in SSP5'', global temperatures increase by 3.69 °C relative to the pre-industrial reference period. Nevertheless,

compared to the SSP' simulations, the differences between SSPs are much smaller. Biophysical constraints thus transform the SSP5 scenario into a fossil-fuel-dependent, low-growth trajectory. The moderate economic convergence tendencies of this scenario—combined with higher resource accessibility compared to SSP2 and SSP3, and lower global warming than in SSP5'—prevent an abrupt economic breakdown during the 21st century, although signs of systemic instability increase, indicating a growing sensitivity of the global system to even small additional deteriorations in the biophysical conditions underpinning socio-economic reproduction.

Fig. 7: a) Total greenhouse gas emissions and b) global average temperature change for SSP2" (blue), SSP3" (beige) and SSP5" (pink).

4. Discussion

4.1. Energy intensity and economic development

The assumption that increasing productive capacity or rising affluence is associated with higher energy efficiency in economic activities—due to factors such as technological know-how or greater investment in research and development—is tied to the idea of relative or even absolute decoupling between economic growth and environmental impacts (B. Dong et al., 2016; Elhaj et al., 2025).

However, while the simulations run with MORDRED 1.0.2 do indeed exhibit a modest relative 'decoupling' as long as the global economy grows, this trend reverses when economic production begins to decline. The resulting dynamics appear across key industries, affecting fossil and biomass energy intensity as well as the intensity of fossil and renewable electricity (Figure 1 in SM1).

Thus, the same assumption that supports a relative decline in environmental pressure during growth also implies an accelerated collapse when the 'business-as-usual'

pathway begins to break down. During growth phases, energy efficiency gains enable further expansion; during contraction, declining productive capacity causes deterioration in sectoral energy efficiencies. A vicious cycle emerges: declining energy efficiency increases demand for energy, which heightens environmental pressure; that, in turn, accelerates degradation, adversely impacts the global economy, reduces production, and further degrades energy efficiency. Although this vicious circle is facilitated by biophysical constraints, it evolves into a self-reinforcing dynamic that cannot be reduced simply to the biophysical factors—and it could, in principle, be interrupted by technological policy or structural changes not modeled here.

Nevertheless, given that most global environmental scenario quantifications do not incorporate historical discontinuities in economic growth (Lauer et al., 2024), we contend that the risks arising from a failure of ‘decoupling’ have been insufficiently emphasized in the literature. Our quantifications of SSP2” and SSP3” demonstrate that decoupling may hold long enough to lock the global economy into a decade-long ‘business-as-usual’ path—but once biophysical feedbacks intensify, the very dynamic of decoupling becomes an accelerator of economic and environmental collapse. Thus, ‘decoupling’ only denotes one side of a positive feedback loop which is overlooked in periods of economic growth but emerges as an additional pressure factor in periods of economic collapse.

Further research is required to refine projections of future energy-intensity trends across sectors and socio-economic scenarios—especially those that allow for historical discontinuities and structural shifts in the global energy–economy system (Edelenbosch et al., 2017; Stern, 2017; Tavoni et al., 2015). This task is complicated by methodological challenges in measuring energy intensity itself: it is defined as the ratio of biophysical energy inputs to monetary output, making it an inherently abstract unit whose concrete material content changes over time (cf. Fiorito, 2013).

4.2. Boundary conditions of SSP quantifications

The results of our SSP implementations reaffirm the importance of model structure and boundary conditions in shaping scenario outcomes (Sognaes et al., 2021). In MORDRED, reproducing results akin to previous SSP quantifications (SSP2’, SSP3’, SSP5’) requires high labor productivity growth assumptions; land productivity growth assumptions significantly higher than the assumptions on future improvements in crop yield made in previous SSP quantifications (Fricko et al., 2017); optimistic assumptions about fossil fuel availability, extraction costs and substitutability between fossil fuels; and, ultimately, the absence of strong climate impacts on labor productivity (Table 1).

In contrast, the boundary conditions for the SSP” simulations assume land productivity improvements more in line with past scenario work, high labor productivity growth, greater skepticism regarding coal/lignite extraction under a favorable EROI, limited substitutability across fossil fuel types, and incorporation of climate impacts on capital, agricultural output, working hours, and labor productivity.

Importantly, the outcomes observed in SSP2", SSP3", and SSP5" will likely be observed only in models with a high degree of endogenization of variables such as world population and economic growth, coupled with feedbacks linking the economy and biophysical environment, and with sectoral disaggregation (via an input–output structure). The latter implies more conservative assumptions about substitutability among energy and sectoral inputs. Consequently, we argue that as IAMs become more holistic and integrate environmental feedbacks more fully, they will tend to project global-level historical discontinuities during the 21st century.

That said, model projections should not be mistaken for precise numerical predictions. The complexity inherent in representing the global system and its long-term trajectories is so great that we can only explore plausible dynamics and pattern shifts, not exact quantitative outcomes. Like all modeling studies, the quantitative outcomes of our scenario exercise must be interpreted in light of the boundary conditions underpinning the simulations. For example, we strongly caution against interpreting SSP5 as the 'best' scenario as it does not show discontinuities as strong as SSP2 and SSP3 when feedback mechanisms are included. Given the high uncertainty regarding climate impacts, the higher level of global warming and fossil fuel dependence in SSP5 could prove disastrous in simulations adopting more pessimistic climate damage parameters. At the same time, in our simulations rising extraction costs of fossil resources play a key role driving the dynamics observed (section 3 SM1) but there are high uncertainties surrounding future developments of this variable. Equally, the model does not explore disaster and emergency policies that presumably would be developed once the economic crisis becomes evident (Nohrstedt & Parker, 2024). These policies might prevent an escalation of mortality rates and a demographic and economic breakdown in the periphery although a recovery and return to economic growth comparable to the beginning of the 21st century seems less plausible. Thus, in general, the conducted analysis principally serves to illustrate that the socio-economic future depicted by previous quantified assumptions of the SSPs is too narrow and that strong historical discontinuities cannot be ruled out *ex ante*. Previous quantifications of the SSPs could generate an unjustified impression of stability, continuity and certainty that dissolves once a more holistic, biophysically grounded and less techno-optimist approach is taken.

4.3. Policy implications

We demonstrate that scenarios that break with the historical linearity and continuity assumed in all SSP storylines, do not only enter into the realm of possible futures but appear highly plausible (Gall et al., 2022). Additionally, we argue that, considering the degree of techno-optimism of the assumptions necessary to 'produce' futures of continued linearity, scenarios featuring significant collapse dynamics of environmental and economic systems appear more probable than scenarios that picture the future as extended present. This finding has a high policy relevance given that policies based on naïve expectations about the viability of 'business-as-usual' are radically different from policies that fully take into account the risks of current environmental and economic

developments (Crownshaw et al., 2019; Jäger et al., 2024; Lawrence et al., 2024; Wesseler & Zhao, 2019).

Currently, global environmental scenarios tend to both underestimate the degree of ecosystem deterioration and climate change caused by continued economic growth, as well as the severity of adverse impacts on economic structures caused by the loss of Earth system support functions. Reorienting policies towards a precautionary approach, thus, implies even higher rates of necessary structural and institutional changes than is currently supposed to prevent drastic climate change. Rather than a ‘decoupling’ of growth from environmental deterioration, these changes would include a ‘decoupling’ of basic human need satisfaction from growth (Brand-Correa & Steinberger, 2017; Buchs et al., 2024; Millward-Hopkins et al., 2020).

Conclusion

In this article we have conducted a comparative scenario analysis of three shared socio-economic pathways (SSP2, SSP3 and SSP5), using a system dynamics based IAM incorporating key feedback mechanisms between global economic, demographic and environmental systems. While a simulation of SSPs without biophysical factors constraining economic growth produces dynamics comparable to previous scenario quantifications using other IAMs, we find that integrating biophysical feedbacks into the quantification of SSPs profoundly alters long-term socio-economic and environmental trajectories, resulting in a global panorama hardly compatible with the global future traced in the original SSP storylines. Rather than a perpetual increase affluence alongside growing environmental impacts, feedback-induced discontinuous developments—manifesting as contractions in production and final demand, population decline, and the spread of poverty—become defining features of 21st-century dynamics in some of the quantified SSP variations. Thus, outcomes from SSP quantifications are shown to be highly sensitive to scenario assumptions and the structure of the IAM used to run the simulations. Importantly, these results do not imply deterministic collapse but rather expose the fragility of the growth-dependent structures embedded in conventional IAM and in the SSP architecture itself. Our findings suggest that the perceived continuity and stability of previous SSP quantifications derive largely from methodological constraints and techno-optimistic assumptions rather than empirical plausibility. As soon as realistic biophysical limits are introduced, the linearity of the original SSPs dissolves, giving way to nonlinear, self-reinforcing dynamics that current policy frameworks remain ill-equipped to address. Consequently, the central policy implication is the urgent need to move beyond the paradigm of “decoupling” growth from environmental degradation and to explore institutional pathways that ensure human well-being independently of economic expansion. Strengthening global resilience under deep uncertainty thus requires reframing scenario design toward precautionary and post-growth perspectives capable of capturing systemic risks. The SSP architecture, while foundational for global environmental assessment, should evolve to integrate non-equilibrium dynamics, feedback-induced discontinuities, and alternative socio-economic imaginaries if it is to remain relevant for policy-making in the Anthropocene.

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